

Type II respiratory immunophlogosis: review of our case series in the light of the Clinical-Cytological-Grading (CGC)

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Abstract: In a recent scientific publication Gelardi and al. described the Clinical-Cytological-Grading as an additional score to be used in association with SNOT-22 et al NPS in the evaluation of patients with chronic sinusitis and nasal polyposis in order to identify those who are correctly eligible for biological therapy in clinical practice. In this paper, the authors review their series of patients with nasal polyposis treated with monoclonal antibodies in order to assess whether the prescription of the therapy was appropriate in the light of the GCC.

Keywords: Chronic Rhinosinosis, nasal polyps, monoclonal antibodies, mepolizumab, dupilumab, Clinical-Cytological-Grading.

1. INTRODUCTION

In a recent scientific publication Gelardi et al described the Clinical-Cytological-Grading as an additional score to be used in association with SNOT-22 et al NPS in the evaluation of patients with chronic sinusitis and nasal polyposis in order to identify those who are correctly eligible for biological therapy in clinical practice. According to Gelardi “ *CCG is a score based on both nasal cytology findings and comorbidities, including asthma, allergy and ASA hypersensitivity. For each variable, a score value was assigned: neutrophilic infiltrate was scored as 1, mast cell infiltrate was scored 1, eosinophilic infiltrate was scored 2 and eosinophilic + mast cell was scored 4; similarly, ASA hypersensitivity scored 1, asthma 2, allergy 2 and ASA sensitivity + asthma 3. The CCG was composed as the sum of these individual scores. CCG global score is classified as low-grade (score 1-3), medium-grade (4-6) and high-grade (≥ 7).* “ (1)(2)(3)(4)(5)(6)(7)(8)(9)(10)(11).

In this paper, the authors review their series of patients with nasal polyposis treated with monoclonal antibodies in order to assess whether the prescription of the therapy was appropriate in the light of the GCC.

2. PATIENTS AND METHODS

As reported in our previous work, From June 2020 to February 2022, 20 patients suffering from nasal polyposis underwent surgery at our Operating Unit and were enrolled in a study to evaluate the efficacy of biological therapy. The minimum follow-up time required for inclusion in the study was 12 months. Within one month of surgery, patients began biological therapy. Twelve patients, all of whom also had bronchial asthma, undertook therapy with mepolizumab. Eight patients, of whom only three also affected by bronchial asthma, undertook therapy with dupilumab.(12)(13)(14)(15)(16)(17)(18)(19)(20)(21)

All patients were screened for endoscopic objectivity classified according to Nasal Polip Score and patient-reported symptoms classified according to SNOT 22 (Sino Nasal Outcome Test) immediately before surgery, immediately after

surgery and before the start of biological therapy, 6 months and 12 months from the beginning of biological therapy.(22)(23)(24)(25)(26)(27)(28)(29)(30)(31)(32)(33)(34)(35)(36)

In the present work the patients were re-evaluated in the light of the GCC found preoperatively in order to establish the correctness of the prescription of biological therapy.

3. OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

In the group of patients undergoing Dupilumab therapy, 5 out of 8 had a CCG score that could be classified as medium-grade (4-6) while 3 out of 8 were in high-grade (> 7). In the group of patients receiving mepolizumab therapy 8 out of 12 were in the high-grade and 4 out of 12 in the medium grade. This significant difference in initial severity based on the GCC is due to the fact that currently Italian legislation allows the prescription of Mepolizumab only for patients suffering from bronchial asthma while direct prescription for nasal polyposis is not yet allowed for which patients treated with Mepolizumab were necessarily severe asthmatic patients with CRSwNP co-morbidities in whom the prescription of the biological drug was carried out by the allergist or pulmonologist specialist and who were followed in our operating unit regarding the post-operative course in the first year after surgery for nasal polyposis.

The results obtained at 6 and 12 months of treatment were excellent both in patients treated with Dupilumab and in those treated with Mepolizumab; there were no substantial differences in the results obtained between high-grade and medium-grade CCG patients.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We believe the GCC is extremely important in identifying patients eligible for biological therapy.

In our case series, the review carried out did not find anomalies or excessive prescriptions, probably because our selection is generally very careful and we limit the prescription of biological drugs only to patients with serious risk of relapse or relapse that has already occurred several times. We routinely carry out nasal cytology in preoperative patients with nasal polyposis, as well as carry out allergological and pneumological examinations and investigate the presence of hypersensitivity to acetylsalicylic acid, so the introduction of CCG does not involve any addition to our normal preoperative habits.

In the very near future, other biological drugs will be authorized for the treatment of nasal polyposis and this type of therapy will become commonly used. The cost of these therapies already poses today and will pose even more in the future a series of pharmaco-economic problems, for which the fact of having an additional evaluation score that allows to correctly filter the insertion of patients in biological therapy avoiding cases of over-treatment, undoubtedly represents a very important advantage in our clinical practice.

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